

IMPORTANCE OF CASE STUDY IN TEACHING EFL

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Annotation: Case study's goal is to check case of something /someone and suggesting reliable solution as doctor checks patient condition and gives recommendation.

Key words: Case study, EFL, ELL, learner, individual learner, strategy, method

Behind the term "Successful learner" in second language acquisition lies Individual Learner Differences which contains age, sex, aptitude, motivation, learning styles, learning strategies and personality. Accomplishing salient research and study works between learner effectiveness and learner differences has been culmination topic among language learners for many years. The current article under the topic of: Learner effectiveness: A cause of learner strategy use? was authored by Ali Akbar Ansarin piloted to scale and answer the role of learner success on language learning strategy use which is considered one of learner factors.

Case study's goal is to check case of something /someone and suggesting reliable solution as doctor checks patient condition and gives recommendation. The researcher also examined learners' effectiveness case on strategy use and after figuring out differences between students, recommended solution as key factors to improve strategy use among less successful learners.

Research procedure and sufficient data collection request from investigator to utilize suitable research methods. Background information concerning learner variables is fulfilled by:

- Predictive method which categorized learners as "good, bad, intelligent etc."

The ladder between early studies and recent ones was connected via:

- Explanatory method which shows reasons of individual learner success in second language acquisition and the casual method was conducted to understand the impact of certain changes in existing standard procedures.

- Descriptive method was used for analysis presentation and table based description.

- Problem-solving method. General meaning of the article was carried out with it because researcher gave key factors for syllabus designers to stabilize less effective and more successful learners' strategy use.

- Quantitative method identified a numerical output that helped to answer research question.

- Qualitative method based on group focus and concerned with written products of submitted exercise.

Here was used some methods for collecting data:

- Questionnaire
- Documents (for students' previous information)
- Focus groups.

After implementing questionnaire developed by Wong and Nunan into research process, 441 first year Azarbaijan University students completed it then author analyzed the result not only in meaningful paragraphs but also in tables. Final stage application was the product of Chi-square test showed alternative hypothesis determined differences between the more and less effective learners' strategy use. Of course Chi-square test was used the evaluation of Test results which showed final numbers 232 more effective and 209 less effective participants emerged.

Collected data led to conclusion part and researcher's solution was for syllabus designers to include teaching materials which is handful for strategy training and learning while doing tasks. In addition teachers also should introduce colorful learning strategies and should train learners to employ them. Furthermore, second language researchers' replication of this study in different educational settings suggested by investigator.

Bachelor degree and teaching experience gave me general or limited comprehension of individual learner differences and strategy use. It means that I did use of methods and taught learners unconsciously even I learned English myself by strategies implicitly. Every single article in this subject opening my mind concerning deep meaning of the terms. Deep meaning ensures answers how to use them? When use them? Why should we use and for whom as well. Especially results of this article taught that suitable strategy is beneficial not only for teaching but also for learning to success in second language acquisition and catching information in an easy way. In addition getting known about chi-square test gave me opinion to analyze results with it in future research works and PHD. As a teacher the article informed me to choose materials according to useful strategy. In addition the article leads ELL to utilize and select right strategies for gaining profound knowledge which directs to be successful learner. Moreover ELL can get know about which strategy is suitable for which task to learn data in a short and convenient way. Conclusion and results will be

concern for learner to become self-directed involvement for developing language learning process.

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